

Being with Oneself as God-Encounter

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I have never used the term ‘quarantine’ till recent times, as far as I remember. When I first read in the newspaper, I had to turn the pages of my dictionary in order to have right comprehension. However, I learnt that it is been an ancient practice for years. In 1377, the first law on medical isolation was passed by the Great Council, when the plague was rapidly running European countries. The law prescribed isolation for 30 days, called a ‘trentino’. Subsequently, many countries adopted similar laws to protect the people. When the duration of isolation was enhanced to 40 days, the name also changed to ‘quarantine’ by adopting the Latin ‘quadraginta’, which referred to a 40-day detention placed on ships. *(I quote from an article published on the center page of a newspaper: The Hindu, April 3, 2020).*

Though the terms ‘quarantine’ and ‘isolation’ are used interchangeably, but they convey two different meanings. Quarantine is imposed to separate and restrict the movement of persons, who may have been exposed to infectious disease, but not yet known to be ill. But Isolation is a complete separation from others of a person known or reasonably believed to infected with communicable diseases. However, these terms did not create any fuss as far as it was a practice of hospitals and homes. But, now, it has become a world-wide practice. We cannot claim it to be one of the scientific practices as it is found in every culture evolved from a practical reasoning.

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A Personal Story

As a school boy, I was affected with smallpox. I was quarantined, isolated; and quiet unfortunate that It was during the time of Christmas vacation. But, my feeling within was of passion week. I yelled at people who visited me to greet me ‘Merry Christmas’. Perhaps, my reaction had reasons; as I had to fight with loneliness, fight with pain; these reasons had developed in me a kind of restlessness which made me feel unloved. Time to time I started to wet my pillow with my tears. It shakes me even today, if I think about it. But now, I can understand that given my age, maturity, time and mood in which I fell sick, it is quite natural to suffer from such feelings.

I realized that it is a precious time given to me to be with oneself and to go within oneself.

But, today, I am surprised that I seem to share the same feelings of then, even though not infected with the disease of COVID-19. I was in Maharashtra, which has the highest number of cases. No worries, no tension, I was at peace in Pune and all along my journey, till I reached Dindigul, Tamil Nadu. The moment, we entered our Jesuit Community, we were quarantined. That developed in us a kind of fear and restlessness. First of all, back from Pune, we had to fight the heat for a day or two. Secondly, Beschi Jesuit Community is said to be our mother house of the province. Almost, every one of us love to come and stay at Beschi till we get old. Obviously, we don’t like stay close to cemetery, when grow old; we might tend to count the days. But this particular stay at Beschi has been very different. I am at Beschi but I am not is the paradox of the situation. I couldn’t enter into the main stream of the community. I usually, enjoy meeting elderly fathers; but couldn’t. I love to see novice moving ahead with regular routine. But everything seemed the other way; no games,

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complete distancing, I seem to dislike my own smell with the mask business and so on. Though, I could understand the seriousness of the disease, on the other hand, it is mainly to help our elderly fathers to have a sound health; but then, it is was difficult when it comes to within. I had to move on otherwise, my fear and restlessness would lead me towards a summer 'stress'. (I will come back to this stress in few lines.)

Facing the 'Within'

'Late have I realized' was my encounter. It was from there; in that difficulty of facing the 'within', I began to move on. I realized that it is a precious time given to me to be with oneself and to go within oneself. Today, a term called "STRESS" has been widely, introduced to people especially, to the educated crowd. People tend to consider stress as psychological disorder. Of course, some say that this stress has become business. I acknowledge that I don't have degree to elaborate the term 'stress'. But as far as I understand, stress is the pre-occupations, worries, tensions which stops me from being with myself, going within myself. Thus, we need to get ourselves out of all the that worries us; instills fear in us; bothers us. As we keep ourselves moving in this direction, one will find himself/herself going deeper into oneself. Not alone, but he/she will automatically allow the spirit to guide us towards a greater consciousness. I feel that this is where I encounter the transcendental being within. This is how the time of quarantine evolved into a God-encounter for me.

But it is just a matter of mindfulness and allowing the inner self to retreat. Of course, to be mindful is not just reading a novel. Mindfulness is a difficult task especially, at this time of confusion, fear and restlessness. We cannot give up because our survival is at risk. Science is not able to answer and solve the problems.

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Conclusion

It might sound like guided-meditation or it might seem like defending the heading. If so, it is correct to be in that status, because it is an experience to me and it is an information to the reader. I don't say that we all should enter into retreat mode, by shutting the outside, keeping silence and so on. But it is just a matter of mindfulness and allowing the inner self to retreat. Of course, to be mindful is not just reading a novel. Mindfulness is a difficult task especially, at this time of confusion, fear and restlessness. We cannot give up because our survival is at risk. Science is not able to answer and solve all the problems we face. Yes, it is not because science can only function as it is supposed to. It cannot bypass anything. Nothing more It has to say or do. Government is trying its best to fight. I find no point in blaming the government for the lack of efficiency to handle the situation. At the end, I am left with nothing but my faith. Faith alone has something to take me forward. If I am to blame my faith then I will be nowhere. Thus, we need to unite this collective consciousness; collective trust; and there we will encounter God who alone can give us the strength to fight the battle.

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